

An Analysis of Native English and Pakistani English Writers' Use of Hedging In Linguistics Research

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Abstract

This corpus-based study comparatively investigates the employment of hedging categories and their linguistic items in the discussion sections of linguistic PhD dissertations written by native English writers (NEWs) writers and Pakistani English Writers (PEWs). Based on the analysis of the two corpora (15 PhD dissertations by NEWs; 15 PhD dissertations by PEWs), overall, findings revealed that NEWs hedge more than their PEWs counterparts. However, findings also showed that both groups displayed a high degree of similarity in using the categories of hedging. Both groups mainly rely on lexical and hedging to lessen the certainty of their claims and arguments, and to a large extent, both groups avoid using adverbs of frequency to hedge their claims. Additionally, epistemic and possibility hedging was not primarily used by the two groups. However, NEWs and PEWs writers differ in the use of the linguistic items of hedging. It is suggested that due to the impact of culture and L1, Pakistani L2 writers tend to be more committed to their claims in order to be more persuasive.

Introduction

Presenting new knowledge and claims is a fundamental function of academic writing in general and PhD dissertations in particular (Fløttum et al., 2006). While writing their PhD dissertations, writers are required to make meaningful and convincing claims that involve evidence and proof. At the same time, they need to present their claims and arguments cautiously to persuade their readers. One way to achieve this is possibly through hedges because using this discourse marker allows writers to lessen the strength and certainty of their claims so that they can influence their audience (Hinkel, 2005; Hyland, 2005).

Hedging is one of the metadiscourse makers employed by writers to make their arguments less authorial and assertive by mitigating the certainty of their propositions (Lee & Deakin, 2016). Hence, the influence of hedging devices in the text (oral or written) can, in turn, affect the meaning or the conveyed message (Taweel, et al, 2011; Khan, Khan, Ullah, Usman, Farhat, 2020). Hyland (1996) points out that "hedging devices are used to indicate a lack of complete commitment to the truth of the proposition, and a desire not to express the commitment categorically (p.115). Hedging is realized by some linguistic devices, such as modal verbs, nouns, adjectives, adverbs and so on (Brown and Levinson, 1987).

It is speculated in the literature that cross-culture variations influence hedging in academic writing (Vassileva, 2001). For instance, the way Anglo-American writers perceive hedging differs from that of Pakistani-speaking English writers. More specifically, Anglo-American tend to hedge more and thus are less committed to the claim, while Arab L2 writers' use of hedging is limited because amplification and confirmation are features of the Pakistani discourse (Hinkel, 2005; Ullah, Malik, Zeb, Rehman, 2019). This kind of "cross-cultural misunderstanding" (Vassileva, 2001) has not been investigated in previous studies on the use of hedging by Arab L2 writers and Anglo-American L1 English writers. It is hoped that the findings may contribute to alleviating the cross-cultural misunderstanding that results from the different perceptions of hedging.

Accordingly, the present study grew out of the gap as mentioned above in earlier research to investigate the use of hedges categories and their linguistic items in the discussion sections of linguistic theses written by EN and PE writers. A comparison is made between the two groups of writers in term of (1) the total frequency of the use of hedging, (2) the patterns of choice of the different hedging categories and (3) the use of linguistic items of hedging. The main objective of this study is to provide an in-depth description of how hedges and their linguistic expressions are used by EN and PE writers. Hence, a better understanding of how hedges are utilized in academic writing for presenting new claims will be provided for Pakistani L2 writers of English. This will, in

turn, contribute to fostering Pakistani L2 writers' L2 pragmatic competence and strategies of making arguments and claims.

To achieve these objectives, this study attempts to answer the following research questions:

1. Do NEWs writers use hedges more than PEWs or vice versa?
2. What are the similarities and differences (if any) between NEWs and PEWs in the use of hedging categories?
3. How are hedges realized linguistically by NEWs and PEWs?

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of hedges

It was Lakoff (1973) who first introduced the term "hedging" in writing. Since the notion of hedging has been studied intensively, it seems there is a consensus on the definition of hedging (Hyland, 1996). Lakoff used the term hedging to indicate fuzziness; "for me some of the most interesting questions are raised by the study of words whose job is to make things more or less fuzzy" (p.195). Some researchers used different terms to refer to the term hedging: vagueness, tentative language, indirectness and uncertainty (Hyland, 1998; Varttala, 2001). Hyland, (1996) defined hedging as "the expression of tentativeness and possibility and it is central to academic writing where the need to present unproven propositions with caution and precision is essential" (p.115).

In essence, hedges can be referred to as the act of mitigating the strength of claims made by writers. Following Hyland (1995), in this study, hedging is concerned with any language devices used by writers to describe "(1) a lack of complete commitment to the truth value of an accompanying proposition or (2) a desire not to express that commitment categorically" (p.1). Hence, words and expressions like *perhaps*, *seems*, *I guess*, *may be*, *kind of* and *sort of* are different forms of hedging. More examples are given in the following section.

Taxonomy of hedging

Different researchers have categorized hedges in different ways. For example, based on their functions, Prince et al. (1982) classify hedging into two types; shields and approximators. The former refers to "hedging devices that do not affect the truth-conditions but reflect the degree of speaker's commitment to the truth-value of the proposition" (e.g., I think, appear) (Markannen& Schroder, 1997, p.12). By contrast, approximators are hedging devices that affect the truth condition, affecting the content itself (e.g., according to) (Markannen& Schroder, 1997, p.13). Salager-Meyer's (1994) taxonomy is a further classification of hedges whereby she added three categories to Prince et al.'s (1982). This classification includes shields (e.g., might, seem, probably, suggest), approximators (e.g., approximately, occasionally), expressions of the authors' personal doubt and direct involvement (e.g., I believe, to our knowledge), emotionally-charged intensifiers (e.g., extremely difficult, absolutely interesting) and compound hedges (e.g., it may suggest that ..., It would seem likely that ...) (Salager-Meyer's, 1994, pp. 154-155). However, these two taxonomies are debatable because they were based on medical corpora, and they are certainly influenced by the nature of the discipline (Varttala 1999).

Another classification to be presented here is Hyland's (1994) classification of hedging based on the grammatical classes. This taxonomy consists of "modal verbs (e.g. can, may, might), lexical verbs (seem, suggest, believe), modal adverbs (often, occasionally, a bit), modal adjectives (few, hardly, just) and modal nouns (possibility, assumption, estimate)" (Hyland, 1994, p.244). Noticeably, this classification is not comprehensive as it does not include assertive pronouns and downtoners, so that it was not considered as an analysis framework for the current study.

Based on both the functions of hedging and part of speech, Hinkel (2005) classifies hedges into six categories: epistemic, lexical, possibility, downtoners, assertive pronouns, and adverbs of frequency. Hinkel (2005, p. 39) provided a further explanation for her six-way classification in the following way:

1. epistemic hedges refer to the limitations of the writer's knowledge (e.g. potentially, probably);
2. lexical hedges are similar to epistemic hedges but cannot modify phrases (e.g. many, several);
3. possibility hedges can also include probability (e.g. perhaps, hopefully);
4. downtoners function to delimit meaning and emotive implication of nouns, verbs, and adjectives (e.g. at all, a bit);
5. assertive pronouns can modify noun phrases (e.g. anybody, somebody); and
6. adverbs of frequency whose vagueness makes them "ubiquitously function as hedges" (e.g. daily, frequently).

Since this classification was based on a study conducted on L1 and L2 essays written by native and nonnative speakers of English, including Pakistani-speaking learners of English, it is obtained in this study, and thus, the corpora data were analyzed according to the hedging categories and their linguistic realizations presented in Table 1. In addition, full verbs category items appeared in the corpora, and they were not included in Hinkel's classification, so these devices were added to analysis framework.

Table1. Hedging categories and their linguistic realizations (Hinkel's 2005, pp. 37-38)

Hedging Categories	Examples
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Epistemic	according to, actually, apparently, indeed, approximately, broadly, clearly, unlikely comparatively, essentially, likely, most, normally, potentially, probably, rarely, somehow, somewhat, theoretically.
Lexical	(at) about, (a) few, in a way, kind of, (a) little + noun, maybe, like, many, more or less, more, most, much, several, something like and sort of.
Possibility	by (any/some) chance, hopefully, perhaps, possible, in (the) case (of), if you/we know/understand (what [pronoun] mean(s)), if you catch/get/understand my meaning/drift, if you know what I mean (to say)
Downtoners	at all, a bit, all but, a good/great deal, almost, as good/well as, at least, barely, basically, enough, fairly, hardly, in the least/slight, just, merely, mildly, nearly, only, partly, partially, practically, pretty (+adjective), quite (+adjective), rather, relatively, scarcely, simply, slightly, somewhat, sufficiently, truly, virtually.
Assertive pronouns	any-word (anybody, anyone, anything), any, some-pronominal (somebody, someone, something), some.
Adverbs of frequency	annually, daily, frequently, monthly, occasionally, per day/month/year, often, regularly, seldom, sometimes, usually, sporadically, weekly, sporadically
Full verbs	seem, appear, suggest, indicate, propose, argue, think, tend, estimate, assume, believe

Previous studies on hedging

A number of cross-cultural, cross-linguistic, single/cross-discipline, and single/cross-genre studies have been conducted to examine the use of hedging in academic writing, be it research articles or master and doctoral dissertations or undergraduate students' essays. Few studies have examined the employment of hedging in academic writing by Pakistani-speaking writers of English in single genres. For example, in a recent study, Al-Mudhaffari, Hussin and Abdullah (2020) investigated the use of hedging devices in 34 applied linguistics research articles written by Yemeni L2 writers of English. Findings of this study showed that Yemeni L2 writers' use of hedging was limited in that they rarely hedge when they formulate their claims. Similarly, Gomaa (2019) examined the use of hedging in the abstracts of 100 English Linguistic master theses written by Pakistani students. The results of this study revealed that the use of hedging by Pakistani L2 writers of English was scarce. This finding was attributed to the students' lack of pragmatic competence and cross-cultural variation.

Several cross-culture comparative studies have been conducted to examine the use of hedging devices in academic writing among native speakers and nonnative speakers of English in different disciplines. For instance, Hinkel (2005) compared the frequencies of using hedging devices among native speakers and nonnative speakers of English in 745 essays. Findings indicated that L2 writers, including Arab L2 writers, use hedging devices highly less than L1 writers, but in oral conversations, L2 writers use hedging devices largely. Similarly, Comparing 20 medical articles written by Sudanese and British writers, ElMalik and Nesi (2008) investigated the distinction of using hedges in one genre, showing that Sudanese and British writers differ in their use of hedging; in particular, hedges were to some extent more in the British L1 articles than the Sudanese L2 articles. In the same line of research, Crompton (2012) comparatively explored the categories of hedging in texts written by Middle East undergraduate students and native English speakers. The results revealed that hedging was used more in the native speakers' texts than in the Middle Eastern students' texts. Abdollahzadeh's (2019) study further investigates the employments of hedging in discussion sections written by three groups of writers: master's dissertations written in English by Iranian and English graduate students of applied linguistics, and research article discussions by professional writers of applied linguistics. Findings showed that both L1 and L2 master graduates hedged highly less than the professional writers. On the whole, it seems that the findings of the aforementioned studies and other studies (e.g., Chen & Zhang, 2017; Demir, 2018; Kafes 2017; RezanejadLari&Mosalli, 2015; Khan, Ullah,;Salager-Meyer, 2011) confirm that L2 writers' employment of hedging is very limited in comparison to English L1 writers.

Several studies were also conducted to examine the use of hedging cross-linguistically. For instance, Akbas and Hardman (2018) compared the use of hedging in the discussion sections of 9 dissertations written by Turkish L1, Turkish L2 and English L1 writers. The results demonstrated that both Turkish L2 writers and English L1 used hedging in a similar way. Similarly, Bonyadi, Gholami, and Nasiri (2012) found that Iranian L2 and English L1 writers' use of hedging was not different, but Iranian L1 writers hedge less than English writers. Examining 60 conclusion sections, Abdollahzadeh (2011) also investigated the use of hedging devices in applied linguistic articles written by Anglo-American and Iranian writers, revealing that hedging devices is almost similar among Anglo-American and Iranian writers. Examining the distribution of hedging devices in

academic writing in three disciplines (medicine, chemistry, and psychology) in the introduction and discussion sections across English and Farsi languages, Falahati (2004) found that hedging devices are used in English research articles more than in Farsi articles, for which this finding was attributed to the type of language and the general nature of discipline. Added to that, based on a corpus of 649 abstracts collected from 8 journals of applied, Hu & Cao (2011) comparatively examined the use of hedging devices in academic article abstracts between Chinese applied linguist writers and English applied linguistics writers. The findings revealed that hedges were used more in abstracts in the English medium than in the Chinese one. This finding was attributed to cross-linguistic/cultural variation and insufficient English proficiency as a foreign/second language. Similarly, in a comparative cross-linguistic study, Martín-Martín (2008) examined the occurrence and frequency of hedging in 40 research articles in clinical and health psychology genres, written in English and Spanish. In general, the findings of this study suggest that English research articles are marked with more hedging devices than those of the Spanish ones especially in the rhetorical sections. Broadly speaking, the nature of the language may have an impact on the distribution of hedging; for example, English L1 writers appear to be more cautious when making claims more than other L1 writers, be Spanish or Farsi.

In conclusion, according to the studies reviewed above, the following points can be outlined: first, none of the above studies has compared the employment of hedging by Arab L2 writers and English L1 writers in an independent study. Although Hinkel' (2005) included some essays written by Arab L2 writers as part of the corpora, these essays were written by undergraduate students; second, most of the cross-cultural studies' findings suggest that L1 writers use hedging devices much better than L2 writers; third, some cross-linguistic studies demonstrated variant results in which hedging devices occur similarly among different writers from different backgrounds; fourth, examining the use of hedges in different disciplines, such as medicine, chemistry, and psychology, resulted in different usage of hedges. More importantly, none of the reviewed studies above has comparatively explored the choice of the patterns of the hedging categories by Pakistani L2 writers and English L1 writers, in which the focus has been on the overall use of hedging. Thus, the impetus of this study is to fill in these research gaps.

METHODOLOGY

Corpora

To address the research questions, thirty PhD dissertations of English linguistics written by NEWs and PEWs speakers (i.e., 15 by NEWs; 15 by PEWs) were selected randomly, and collected from ProQuest database. All the selected dissertations were submitted between 2011 and 2018, and their length is around 70000–80000 words. To obtain consistency, all dissertations' structure was followed the IMRD standard format (Introduction, Method, Results, Discussion/Conclusion). All the Pakistani English nonnative writers did their PhD. The 15 native English writers were American and British, Anglo-Americans. A number of criteria were used to identify the native English writer, namely their first and last names, their online CVs and biographies and their Twitter and Facebook accounts.

The only part of these dissertations to be analyzed was the discussion section because this portion is the one where graduate students state their claims and opinions as Hyland (1998) stated “ it is in discussions that authors make their claims, consider the relevance of results and speculate about what they might mean, going beyond their data to offer the more general interpretation. . . . , the level of generality, and therefore the density of hedges, is much higher here, as writers explore the ratifications of their results” (p.154). Moreover, examining the use of hedging in one discipline will provide clear clarifications for the variations in using the hedging discourse marker.

Procedures and data analysis

This study focuses on the discussion sections of the selected theses. First, Microsoft word was used to account the number of words in the discussion section of each thesis. The running words in the corpus of the NEWs dissertations consisted 49,601 while the corpus of the PEWs 46,593. Second, specific categories of hedging and their linguistic means were analyzed (epistemic, lexical, possibility, downtoners, assertive pronouns and adverbs of frequencies and full verbs hedges) (see Table 1 in section 2.2) in both corpora.

The hedging devices of each type in NEWs and PEWs dissertation were counted separately to get the frequency rates of their use in both corpora. To find out how similar or different hedging devices are used by NEWs and PEWs writers, the hedging devices' occurrences include epistemic, lexical, possibility, assertive pronouns, frequency adverbials, downtoners and full verbs in the corpora were tagged by TagAnt software after this AntConc software was used to retrieve the frequencies through the keywords and phrases search terms. Then the total number of each hedging devices was computed by Microsoft Excel Program. To establish a balance between the two corpora, the original hedging frequency was calculated per 1000 words for comparison.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution of the hedging categories across the NEWs and PEWs corpora

The purpose of this analysis is two-fold: (1) to present the overall frequencies of the use of the hedging categories by NEWs and PEWs and (2) to present the patterns of choice of various categories of hedging by the two groups.

Table 2 shows that the overall frequency of hedging in the NEWs corpus is 21.06 per 1000 words, far higher than that in the PEWs corpus, 12.96 per 1000 words. This result indicates that PEWs doctoral students used less hedges than NEWs doctoral students. Thus, we suggest that PEWs tend to be less tentative in stating a claim when interpreting the research findings in the discussion sections. This finding supports earlier research which shows that L2 writers may not be ultimately competent to employ language means in order to lessen the certainty of their claims (e.g., Crompton, 2012; Hinkel, 2005; Ho & Li 2018; Hyland & Milton, 1997; Rezanejad, Lari, & Mosalli, 2015; Shaikh, Channar, & Shaikh, Ullah, 2021; Yang, 2013; ElMalik&Nesi, 2008). A further explanation for the insufficient use of hedging by NEWs could be a culturally-oriented factor whereby Pakistani inherently seem to prefer to be assertive and direct without mitigating the certainty of their claims and arguments to reach a high degree of persuasion (Hinkel 2005; Hyland 2005). Hence, L2 Pakistani writers may attempt to strengthen their claims to be more persuasive. The effect of this cross-cultural variation in marking certainty (Vassileva, 2001) is evident in the apparent difference between NEWs and PEWs writers. The limitedness of hedging employment in the L2 English academic writing by Pakistani-speaking writers is confirmed in some previous single genre studies (e.g., Al-Mudhaffari, Hussin& Abdullah, 2020; Gomaa, 2019; Ullah, Shaikh, Channar, & Shaikh, 2021). Moreover, the nature of the writers' L1 (Pakistani) might affect their distribution of hedging as found in previous studies of other languages (Akbas, & Hardman, 2018; Bonyadi, Gholami, & Nasiri, 2012; Hu & Cao 2011; Martín-Martín, 2008). However, the effect of Pakistani requires further investigations, exploring how Pakistani L1 writers hedge their claims compared to English L1 writers.

Table 2. Frequency and distribution of the hedging categories used by NE and PNNE writers

Hedging Categories	NE Writers		PEW writers		
	Freq.	Freq. per 1000 words	Freq.	Freq. per 1000 words	
Epistemics	130	2.62	69	1.48	
Lexical	437	8.81	260	5.58	
Possibility	51	1.03	36	0.77	
Downtoners	232	4.68	106	2.28	
Assertive pronouns	154	3.10	35	0.75	With
Frequency Adverbs	32	0.65	13	0.28	regard to
Full verbs	9	0.18	85	1.82	the
Total	1045	21.06	604	12.96	pattern
					of

choice of various categories of hedging, Table 2 reveals that NE writers and their PEWs counterparts showed, to a large extent, a degree of similarity in the choice of hedging categories. Lexical hedges were the most frequent in both NEWs and PEWs corpora with frequencies of 8.81 and 5.58 per 1000 words, respectively. The next likely hedging category to be employed in the two corpora was downtoners, with frequency rates of 4.68 and 2.28 per 1000 words, respectively. After downtoners, assertive hedging were preferred by NE writers, whereas the PE writers' third choice was full verbs. Epistemics and possibility hedging came in the fourth and fifth positions in the two corpora. Finally, the least frequent hedging category in the NE discussion sections was full verbs whereas adverbial hedging was the least frequent marker in the PEWs discussion sections.

Based on these findings, it is suggested that both NE and PE writers tend to use lexical hedges for presenting their claims and arguments predominantly. It is also noticeable that NE and PE writers consider downtoners as an essential means of their tentative language. Epistemic and possibility hedging seem to be secondary devices in the two corpora. Adverbial hedging devices were not essential means for both native and non-native writers.

The dominance of the lexical hedges in the two corpora could be attributed to their prevalence in English, particularly in formal writing i.e., this category constitutes the largest classes of the mitigation devices (Hinkel, 2005). Downtoners were the next class of hedging to be employed by both groups, which is not congruent with previous studies (Hinkel, 2005). This suggests that that both NE and PE writers prefer to reduce the degree of generalization of their claims. The occurrence rate of the assertive pronouns was higher in the NE corpus than the PNNE corpus, which means that native writers compose their opinion using this hedging marker to mitigate the generalizations degree of their claims (Hinkel, 2005). PE writers did not rely on assertives to hedge claims in their discussion because such devices are not commonly used in Pakistani writing. Moreover, assertive pronouns are used to convey vagueness and give writers the chance to express their claims in a common way (Hinkel, 2002). The uses of adverbial hedging were the most infrequently used in the two corpora because they are to some extent few in spoken and written discourses (Channell, 1994).

In short, the data in Table 2 demonstrate that PEWs writers are more committed to propositions and claims than PE writers as they employed hedging categories less than the NEWs did. The culture-driven factors may contribute to the underuse of hedging by PE writers. Both L1 and L2 writers largely restricted their use of hedging to lexical and downtonres hedging. Epistemic and possibility hedging were not prioritised when making knowledge claims and stating suggestions and conclusions by both groups of writers. Finally, adverbial hedging

devices were rarely used by both native and Pakistani non-native English writers. The following sections present the linguistic items of hedging used by NE and PE writers.

Linguistic items of some hedging categories

This part aims to analyse the use of linguistic items, hedging devices in the two corpora categories. Our focus here is on the highest-ranked linguistic items where comparison is applicable, so assertive pronouns category is not included.

Linguistic items of epistemic hedges

Table 3 shows that the epistemic hedging device ‘*mostly*’ was the most frequently used item in both corpora, with 14% difference in favor of the NE data (25% and 11%, respectively). Then the form ‘*likely*’ occurred 25 times (13%) in the NE data and 12 times (6%) in the PEWs data. The epistemic ‘*according to*’ was also used in different rates in both NE and PE corpora (10% and 5%, respectively). The item ‘*apparently*’ did not occur in the NE data while it rarely occurred in the PEWs data (0% and 4%, respectively). The devices ‘*comparatively*, ‘*essentially* and ‘*potentially*’ were not used at all by PE writers, whereas NE writers relatively used them. Some other epistemic devices such as ‘*normally* and ‘*somehow*’ were not used at all by both NE and PE writers.

Table 3. The linguistic items of epistemic hedging

Epistemic hedging	NE Writers		PE writers	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
mostly	49	25%	21	11%
likely	25	13%	12	6%
according to	19	10%	9	5%
actually	13	7%	7	4%
clearly	9	5%	7	4%
somewhat	9	5%	3	2%
unlikely	6	3%	3	2%
apparently	0	0%	7	4%
normally/somehow	0	0%	0	0%

Linguistic items of lexical hedging

Of all the lexical hedges, as Table 4 illustrates, the form ‘*more*’ was used more frequently by both NE and PE writers with different frequency rates, but it was used far greater by EN than PE writers (41% and 20%, respectively). Similarly, the hedging marker ‘*at about*’ appeared to be widely used by NE writers, while PE writers rarely appeared to employ it. The lexical means ‘*most*’ used less frequently by PEWs (8%) than NE (6%). Reversely, ‘*may be*’ was highly marked by PEWs in conjunction with NE writers (5% and 1% in that order). Some lexical hedges like ‘*sort of* and ‘*something like*’ did not occur in the PEWs data; however, they rarely occurred in the NE data. The only lexical marker that was not used by both NE and PE writers was the form ‘*in a way*’.

Table 4. The linguistic items of lexical hedging

Epistemic hedging	NE Writers		PE writers		Linguistic items of
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
more	192	41%	94	20%	of
(at) about	41	9%	8	2%	
most	38	8%	30	6%	
a little + a noun	12	3%	6	1%	
may be	3	1%	24	5%	
kind of	2	0%	4	1%	
more or less	0	0%	12	3%	
in a way	0	0%	0	0%	

possibility hedging

As shown in Table 5, the most common linguistic expression in both corpora was the marker ‘*possible*’ with a higher percentage in the EN data (45% in the NE and 26% in the PNNE data). ‘*Perhaps*’ was also used more frequently by EN writers than PNNE writers (24% and 12% correspondingly). Interestingly, the possibility linguistic means, such as ‘*by some chance*, ‘*if you understand*, ‘*if you catch my meaning* and ‘*if you know what I mean*’ did not occur at all in the NE data while they occurred slightly in the PNNE data. One of the possibility hedging devices that did not occur in both NE and PNNE data is the device ‘*hopefully*’.

possibility	NE Writers		PE writers	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%

possible	33	45%	19	26%	Table 5. The linguistic items of possibility hedging
perhaps	12	16%	2	3%	
in case of	6	8%	0	0%	
hopefully	0	0%	0	0%	
by some chance, if you understand, if you catch my meaning and if you know what I mean	0	0%	1	1%	

Linguistic items of downtoner hedges

Table 6 shows that the most frequently used downtoners marker was ‘*only*’ in both NEWs and PEWs corpora, but it occurred more frequently in the NE data than the PEWs data (45% and 32%, respectively). ‘*Just*’ was also preferred by EN writers more than PNNE writers with 4% difference. Some of the downtoners linguistic devices like ‘*sufficiently, merely, and barely*’ did not occur in both corpora. Some other downtoners devices occurred in the NE data but not in the PEWs data and the vice versa.

Table 6. The linguistic items of downtoners hedging

Downtoners	NE Writers		PE writers		Linguistic items of adverb of frequency
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
only	105	50%	34	16%	
just	13	6%	2	1%	
at all	10	5%	3	1%	
at least	10	5%	3	1%	
somewhat	8	4%	4	2%	
relatively	5	2%	3	1%	
a bit	3	1%	0	0%	
almost	3	1%	4	2%	
sufficiently, merely, and barely	0	0%	0	0%	

frequency

Table 7 shows that the adverb ‘*often*’ was the most salient marker in both corpora; however, it appeared much more frequently in the EN data than the ENNS (33% and 9%, respectively). The adverbs ‘*sometimes and frequently*’ were the second and third choices by both groups, with higher percentages in the EN data. Some adverbs of frequency, such as ‘*weekly, seldom, regularly, occasionally and annually*’ were absent in the ENNS data and in the EN data, too.

Table 7. The linguistic items of some adverb of frequency hedging

Adverbs of frequency	NE Writers		PE writers		Linguistic items of full verbs hedges
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
often	15	33%	4	9%	
sometimes	10	22%	3	7%	
frequently	8	18%	2	4%	
occasionally	3	7%	0	0%	
weekly, seldom, regularly, occasionally and annually	0	0%	0	0%	

Table 8 shows that full verbs were not preferred by NE writes, whereas PE writers highly marked them. For example, the verb ‘*seem*’ occurred 30 times (48%) in the PEWs data, it was completely absent in the NE data. Likewise, the verbs ‘*believe and suggest*’ also accounted for 30% in the PE data and 5% in the NE corpus. Both NE and PE writers did not use the verbs ‘*tensed, propose, estimate and argue*’ in these corpora.

Table 8. The Linguistic Items of Some Full Verbs

Full verbs	NE Writers		PE writers	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
seem	0	0%	30	48%
believe	0	0%	10	16%
assume	2	3%	2	3%
suggest	3	5%	9	14%

estimate	0	0%	0	0%
<i>tend, propose, estimate and argue</i>	0	0%	0	0%

In short, the percentages of the linguistic items used in both corpora showed a mixed picture. For example, it was found that terms like *'possible'*, *'more'* and *'often'* were the preferable linguistic means by both NE and PE, but these hedges appeared much less frequently in the PE discussion sections. It was found that, as a second choice, NE writers also rely on linguistic expressions like, *'mostly'*, *'sometimes'*, *'frequently'*, *'perhaps'*, *'likely'*, *'according to'*, *'at about'* and *'most'*. On the other hand, PE writers largely used full verbs like *'seem'*, *'believe'*, *'suggest'* and *'appear'* to mitigate the certainty of their claims, whereas NE writers appeared, to a large extent, not to depend on such verbs. This finding is inconsistent with Hyland' (1998) findings, in which these hedges were the most common expressions for mitigating claims in scientific research articles. Added to this, Linguistic expressions like *'tend'*, *'propose'*, *'estimate'* and *'argue'* were not used at all by both groups, and this supports Varttala's (1999) finding, whereby American writers do not prefer such terms in their scientific articles. The linguistic items, *'sometimes'*, *'most'*, *'likely'* and *'according to'* were not common in the PEWs writers because they may occur more in spoken discourse than written prose (Channell, 1994; Hinkel, 2005). Moreover, adverbs of frequency like *'weekly'*, *'seldom'*, *'regularly'*, *'occasionally'* and *'annually'* were not employed by both NE and PE writers, by which this finding is not congruent with the findings of (Channell, 1994) in that these adverbs are more common in conversations. To sum up, NE and PE writers differ in the use of hedging linguistic expressions.

CONCLUSION

The present study compares the use of hedging categories and their linguistic items in the discussion sections of NE and PE PhD dissertations. The findings showed that, altogether, the NE writers hedge more than their PE counterparts. However, it was found that both groups displayed, to some extent, a degree of similarity in the choice of hedging categories. Lexical hedges were the most widely used in both NE and PE writers corpora, followed by downtoners. Epistemic and possibility hedging were not given a priority when making knowledge claims by both groups of writers. Finally, adverbial hedging means were rarely used by both native and Pakistani non-native English writers. The linguistic items of the hedging categories were used differently in the two groups, except the linguistic items, *possible, more often*, which were the preferable linguistic means by both NE and PE, although they appeared much less frequently in the PEWs data.

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